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Direct Infusion Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study	Impact of early vs. late time-restricted eating on lipid metabolism in women with overweight or obesity		
Document creation date	04/09/2025	Corresponding Email	olga.ramich@dife.de
Principal investigator	Prof. Dr. Olga Ramich	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Untargeted
Institution	Lipotype GmbH	Clinical	No

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes
pH adjustment	None	Special conditions	-
2-phase system	MTBE	Derivatization	-

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium acetate	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS1	1
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Recording mode of raw data at MS1	Centroid mode
MS type	Orbitrap	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1
MS vendor	Thermo	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	High resolution
Direct type	Chip	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS2	17500
MS Level	MS1, MS2	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS2	3
Mass resolution for detected ion at MS1	High resolution	Recording mode of raw data at MS2	Centroid mode
Resolution at m/z 200 at MS1	280000	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Extraction blank	Type of QC sample	Reference material

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Precision	Yes
Lipid recovery	Yes	Accuracy	No
Dynamic quantification range	Yes	Guidelines followed	None
Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	Yes		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Available on request	Raw data upload	No
Are metadata available?	No	Additional comments	-

Sample Descriptions

ChronoFast plasma samples / Human / Plasma

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage time (month)	6
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Freeze-thaw cycles	1
Time to separate plasma/serum (min)	60	Additives	None
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	Yes
Time to freeze (min)	15	Type of preservation method	EDTA
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) HexCer[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	HexCer	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO]-	Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

1) HexCer[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
HexCer 18:1;2/12:0,0	HexCer		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

2) LPC[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO]-	Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

2) LPC[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LPC 12:0;0	LPC		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

3) Cer[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Cer	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO]-	Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

3) Cer[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
Cer 35:1;2	Cer		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

4) SM[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SM	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO]-	Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

4) SM[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
SM 30:1;2	SM		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

5) LPC O[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC O	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO]-	Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

5) LPC O[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LPC 12:0;0	LPC O		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

6) LPC P[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC P	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO]-	Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

6) LPC P[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LPC 12::0	LPC P		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

7) LPE O[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE O	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

7) LPE O[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LPE 17:1;0	LPE O		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

8) LPE P[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE P	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

8) LPE P[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LPE 17:1;0	LPE P		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

9) LPE[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

9) LPE[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LPE 17:1;0	LPE		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

10) ST[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	ST	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

10) ST[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
CHOL D6	ST		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

11) PC[M+CH3COO]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO] ⁻	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Fragment name			
FA1(-H)-			
FA2(-H)-			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	No	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

11) PC[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PC 17:0;0, 17:0;0	PC		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

12) PC O[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC O	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Fragment name			
FA2(-H)-			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	No	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

12) PC O[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PC 17:0;0, 17:0;0	PC O		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

13) PC P[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC P	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Fragment name			
FA2(-H)-			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	No	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

13) PC P[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PC 17:0;0, 17:0;0	PC P		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

14) PE[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Fragment name			
FA1(-H)-			
FA2(-H)-			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	No	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

14) PE[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PE 17:0;0, 17:0;0			
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

15) PE O[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE O	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Fragment name			
FA2(-H)-			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	No	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

15) PE O[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PE 17:0;0,17:0;0	PE O		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

16) PE P[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE P	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Fragment name			
FA2(-H)-			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	No	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

16) PE P[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PE 17:0;0,17:0;0	PE P		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

17) PI[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PI	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Fragment name			
FA1(-H)-			
FA2(-H)-			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	No	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

17) PI[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PI 16:0;0,16:0;0	PI		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

18) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CE	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Fragment name			
Cholesterol			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	No	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

18) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
CE 27:1;0,20:0;0	CE		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

19) DG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DG	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Fragment name			
FA1			
FA2			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	No	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

19) DG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
DG 17:0;0,17:0;0	DG		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

20) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Fragment name			
FA1			
FA2			
FA3			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	No	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

20) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
TG 17:0;0,17:0;0,17:0;0	TG		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		